

CODEN [USA]: IAJPBB

ISSN : 2349-7750

**INDO AMERICAN JOURNAL OF
PHARMACEUTICAL SCIENCES**

SJIF Impact Factor: 7.187

Available online at: <http://www.iajps.com>

Research Article

**FORMULATION AND EVALUTION OF THE GLICLAZIDE
MICROCAPSULES BY EMPLOYING IONIC GELATION
TECHNIQUE.****Chukka Bhargavi, B.Bhagyasri , Dr. M. B .Venkatapathi Raju**Avanthi Institute of Pharmaceutical Sciences, Cherukupally (vil), Chittivalasa (P.O),
Bhogapuram (M), Vizianagaram (Dist.)-531162, A.P.**Article Received:** December 2020**Accepted:** December 2020**Published:** January 2021**Abstract:**

Gliclazide is an oral hypoglycemic agent used in the treatment of non-insulin dependent diabetes mellitus (NIDDM). Among the people who are suffering from long term disorders, the major had been categorized under the people who are suffering from diabetes and a dosage form is needed for them that should provide continuous therapy and should have a high margin of safety. Microencapsulation plays a great role in providing such a kind of dosage form. Gliclazide microspheres with a coat consisting of alginate and Guar gum were prepared by orifice-ionic gelation method and emulsification gelation technique. In the present investigation an attempt was made to develop gliclazide floating microcapsules by employing natural cross linking agents i.e egg shell solution, with a view to prolong the gastric residence time. Orifice ionic gelation technique was used to prepare microcapsules by employing sodium alginate as polymer. Studies were carried out on influence of formulation variables on drug release rate, entrapment efficiencies and floating behavior. The formulated microcapsules were characterized for their micrometric properties, floating properties, drug loading and entrapment efficiency and invitro drug release studies. The gliclazide microcapsules formulated by employing the core: coat (1:1) and having the composition 1.5%v/v acetic acid, 55.55%w/w sodium bicarbonate, 2% w/v sodium alginate, 150ml of 0.1M egg shell solution as curing agent, and by maintaining 48hrs curing time showed required drug release upto 12hrs.

Keywords: *Gliclazide , microspheres , ionic gelation technique , acetic acid, sodium bicarbonate, sodium alginate and egg shell*

Corresponding author:**Chukka Bhargavi**pharmamadhuphd@gmail.com

8328601969

QR code

Please cite this article in press Chukka Bhargavi et al, *Formulation And Evalution Of The Gliclazide Microcapsules By Employing Ionic Gelation Technique.*, Indo Am. J. P. Sci, 2021; 08(1).

INTRODUCTION:

Gliclazide is an oral hypoglycemic second generation sulfonyl urea drug which is useful for a long-term treatment of non-insulin dependent diabetes mellitus (NIDDM). For an oral hypoglycemic drug to be effective, rapid absorption from the gastrointestinal tract is required. However, the absorption rate of gliclazide from the gastrointestinal tract is slow and varied among the subjects, due to either poor dissolution of gliclazide owing to its hydrophobic nature or poor permeability of the drug across the GI membrane. Incorporation of gliclazide in controlled release dosage forms such as alginate beads may control its absorption from the gastrointestinal tract and overcome the variability problems. To control the release rate and improve the absorption across GI membrane of gliclazide microencapsulation technique is employed.

Calcium carbonate obtained from natural source is more stable comparing with the CaCO_3 from synthetic source it was evident from the thermo gravimetric analysis that industrial calcium carbonate decomposes at a temperature of about 30°C less than the calcium carbonate obtained from natural source.

METHOD AND METHODOLOGY:

Determination of the λ_{max} :

Accurately weighed amount of gliclazide (25mg) was dissolved in 10 ml of acetonitrile and further diluted with 0.1N HCl up to 25ml. Then the solution was scanned for maximum absorbance in UV double beam spectrophotometer in the range from 200 to 400nm using 0.1N HCl as blank. The λ_{max} of the drug was found to 226.5 nm.

Preparation of standard solution of gliclazide:

Accurately weighed amount of gliclazide (25 mg) was transferred to a 25 ml volumetric flask, dissolved in acetonitrile and the volume was adjusted up to themark.

Procedure: The standard solution of gliclazide was subsequently diluted with 0.1N HCl to obtain a series of dilutions containing 2,4,6,8 and 10 μg of gliclazide per ml of solution. The absorbance of these solutions was measured in Shimadzu double beam UV spectrophotometer at 226.5 nm using 0.1N HCl as blank. The concentration of gliclazide and the corresponding absorbance values are given in Table 4.3. The absorbance values were plotted against concentration of gliclazide as shown. The method obeyed Beer's law in the concentration range of 2-10 $\mu\text{g}/\text{ml}$.

PREFORMULATION STUDIES:**Infrared spectroscopic studies:**

Fourier- Transformed Infrared (FT-IR) spectra were obtained on Bruker FT-IR system. The scanning range was $400\text{-}4000\text{ cm}^{-1}$.

Preparation of gliclazide floating microspheres:

The floating microspheres containing Gliclazide were prepared by orifice ionic gelation technique. Sodium alginate, acetic acid and the sodium bicarbonate were dispersed in the purified water to form homogenous polymer mixture. The API, Gliclazide was added to the polymer dispersion and mixed thoroughly on a magnetic stirrer to form homogenous dispersion. The resulting dispersion was dropped separately in each case through a 20mm syringe needle into 150 ml of 0.1M above curing reagent solutions and was allowed to retain in solution for curing up to 48hrs. The microcapsules were then separated by filtration, washed three times with deionised water and dried at room temperature for 24 hrs. The microcapsules of gliclazide were also formulated with different concentrations of sodium alginate & sodium bicarbonate. The composition and the conditions observed during the preparation of microcapsules are showed. The prepared microcapsules were characterized optically in terms of morphology by using trinocular microscope under $40\times$ magnifications. The photomicrographs were observed .

Determination of Rheological properties:

Optimized formulation of gliclazide microcapsules was subjected to the determination of following rheological properties:

Bulk density & Tapped density:

Bulk density and tapped density were measured by using 10 ml graduated cylinder. The previously weighed sample was placed in a cylinder and its initial volume recorded and then subjected to tapping mechanically for 100 times, the corresponding tapped volume was noted down. Bulk density and tapped density were calculated from the following formulae:

Angle of repose:

About 2gms of microcapsules were transferred into a hollow cylinder which was placed on a graph sheet. Then the cylinder was slowly lifted. The height and diameter of the heap formed were noted down. The angle of repose was calculated by the following formula.

$$\theta = \tan^{-1} h/r$$

Where r is the radius and h is the height.

Drug content:

Microcapsules containing 10 mg of gliclazide were weighed and crushed to fine powder in a mortar and was extracted with 10 ml of acetonitrile. The slurry was filtered and the filtrate was made up to 100 ml with in 0.1N HCl. One milliliter of the sample was collected, suitably diluted with phosphate buffer pH 7.4, and the absorbance was measured at 226.5 nm.

In vitro drug release study:

Microcapsules containing equivalent to 30 mg of gliclazide were subjected to *in vitro* drug release studies. Release of gliclazide from the beads was studied in 0.1N HCl using a USP TDL-08L dissolution test apparatus (Shimadzu, Mumbai) with a rotating basket stirrer operated at 100 ± 2 rpm and temperature was maintained at $37 \pm 1^\circ\text{C}$. Then at regular intervals of time (30 min), 5 ml of samples were collected and same volume was replenished with fresh dissolution medium. The withdrawn samples were filtered through what man filter paper (no.41), suitably diluted and analyzed spectrophotometrically at a λ_{max} of 226.5 using Shimadzu UV-1700 double beamspectrophotometer.

Preformulation studies:

Confirmation studies of gliclazide:

The absorption spectrum of drug solution having a concentration of $10 \mu\text{g/ml}$ was prepared with 0.1N HCl and it was scanned between 200-400nm. The absorption spectrum was noted at 226.5nm. The reported λ_{max} for gliclazide was in between 226-227nm¹; hence the drug used in this investigation was confirmed as gliclazide.

Recovery studies:

Though there are several unofficial reported methods for the estimation of gliclazide from bulk and pharmaceutical dosage forms, still there is need to validate the analytical method as there is a possible interference of excipients in the estimation of drug from formulations proposed in this investigation was determined and the results are tabulate. The data clearly indicated that the excipients are not interfering in the selected method and the same method can be employed for the estimation of gliclazide from the formulations.

Formulation studies:

The floating microcapsules of gliclazide were prepared by ionic gelation technique employing sodium alginate as a polymer.

Studies on influence of concentration of sodium bicarbonate on drug entrapment efficiency and drug release rate of gliclazide:

To study the influence of concentration of gas forming agent (sodium bicarbonate) on entrapment efficiency, drug release and floating properties, three different concentrations of sodium bicarbonate (36, 55.55, 67% w/w) were used to prepare microcapsules.

The formulated microcapsules are subjected to various physical parameters and results were shown. The entrapment efficiency and total floating time was found to be same for all three concentrations.

All the formulations were subjected to Invitro dissolution studies in 0.1N HCl. The dissolution data was presented in Table . and the comparative dissolution profile was depicted.

The drug release followed zero order kinetics as the graph drawn in between Amount drug released Vs time was found to be linear . The correlation coefficient 'r' values observed from the zero order equation and first order equation are showed. The exponential coefficient values from the Peppas plots were in between 0.5 to 1 and hence mechanism of drug release was found to be non fickian diffusion. The values of T50 (time taken for 50% drug release), T90 (time taken for 90% drug release) and release rate constant (K) for all the formulations are indicated.

ANNOVA (one-way) studies have been conducted for floating lag timeshows at the level of $P=0.0006$ reveals that there is a significant change in the release .

As the concentration of sodium bicarbonate increases the drug release rate from the formulated microcapsules increases. Based on the entrapment efficiency, total floating time and drug release rate 55.55%w/w sodium bicarbonate was optimized for preparing floating microcapsules of gliclazide.

Studies on effect of core: coat on drug release and entrapment efficiencies of gliclazide:

To study the influence of core: coat ratio on entrapment efficiency, drug release rate & floating behavior, three different core: coat ratios (1:1, 1:0.75, 1:0.5) were used to prepare floating microcapsules.

The microcapsules formulated with three different ratios were evaluated for various physical parameters and results were shown. The entrapment efficiencies for all the formulations were found to be good and the flow properties were found to be excellent.

All the formulations were subjected to invitro dissolution studies in 0.1N HCl. The dissolution data

was presented in Table 5.6. and the comparative dissolution profile was depicted .

The drug release followed zero order kinetics as the graph drawn in between Amount drug released Vs time was found to be linear. The correlation coefficient 'r' values observed from the zero order equation and first order equation are showed . The exponential coefficient values from the Peppas plots were in between 0.5 to 1 and hence mechanism of drug release was found to be non fickian diffusion. The values of T50 (time taken for 50% drug release), T90 (time taken for 90% drug release)and release rate constant (K) for all the formulations are indicated. ANNOVA (one-way) studies has been conducted for dissolution rate constant shows at level of $P < 0.0001$ which reveals that there is a significant change in the release.

The drug release rate was found to be reduced with increased core: coat ratio. Incase of 1:1 the drug release was prolonged upto 12hrs which is suitable for controlled release drug delivery systems. Based on the entrapment efficiency, drug release and floating behavior 1:1 core: coat ratio was optimized for preparing floating microcapsules, as it offers good entrapment efficiency, slow and complete release of gliclazide.

In the next step, the above optimized formulae by considering the factors like concentration of sodium bicarbonate and 1:1core: coat ratio formulated by using synthetic CaCO_3 as cross linking agent has been replaced with natural cross linking agents like egg shellsolution.

The microcapsules formulated with natural cross linking agent was evaluated for various physical parameters and results were shown . The entrapment efficiencies and the flow properties for the formulation was found to be good and the results were shown.

the formulation was subjected to invitro dissolution studies in 0.1N HCl. The dissolution data was presented and the dissolution profiles was depicted .

The drug release follows zero order kinetics for the natural cross linking agent and the graph was drawn in between Amount drug released Vs time was found to be linear. The correlation coefficient 'r' value observed from the zero order equation and first order equation are showed.

ANNOVA (one-way) studies has been conducted for dissolution rate constant for the entire three different natural cross linking agent with synthetic

CaCO_3 shows at level of $P < 0.0001$ which reveals that there is a significant change in the release . The results were once again compared by conducting t-test (non-parametric) study which shows at level $P < 0.0001$ which once again reveals that there is a significant change in the release .

Based on the above results the three natural cross linking agents shows good entrapment efficiency and flow properties. It also reveals that it offer prolonged and complete drug release than that of the synthetic CaCO_3 .

In the next step, the optimized formulations by using natural cross linking agent was compared with marketed MR tablets (Diamicon). the formulation was subjected to invitro dissolution studies in 0.1N HCl. The dissolution data was presented and the dissolution profiles was depicted .

The drug release follows zero order kinetics for the three different natural cross linking agents with marketed MR tablets (Diamicon) and the graphs were drawn in between Amount drug released Vs time was found to be linear. The correlation coefficient 'r' values observed from the zero order equation and first order equation are showed. The exponential coefficient values from the Peppas plots were in between 0.5 to 1 and hence mechanism of drug release was found to be non fickian diffusion. The values of T50 (time taken for 50% drug release), T90 (time taken for 90% drug release) and release rate constant (K) for the formulation is indicated in Table. The following characteristic peaks were observed in gliclazide and microcapsules containing gliclazide.

The spectra's of both gliclazide and gliclazide microcapsules were compared and results concluded that there was no interaction observed. C=O stretching was observed in case of gliclazide and its microcapsules at 1705.86 cm^{-1} and 1705.19 cm^{-1} , 1703.07 cm^{-1} and 1692.10 cm^{-1} respectively. 2° N-H stretching was observed in case of gliclazide and its microcapsules at 3269.42 cm^{-1} and 3390.05 cm^{-1} , 3391.99 cm^{-1} , 3390.40 cm^{-1} respectively.

The above results reveals that the formulated floating microspheres shows prolonged drug release for about 12hrs than that of the marketed tablets (Diamicon) which shows drug release only for about 6hrs. The results are again compared by conducting t-test (non-parametric) study shows at the level $P < 0.0001$ (for the natural cross linking agent) and $P = 0.0011$ (for

synthetic CaCO₃) reveals that there is a significant difference in drug release .

The similarity factor for the formulations prepared by employing three natural cross linking agent was compared with marketed MR tablets (Diamicron) was below 50 which indicates that the natural cross linking agents are dissimilar with marketed MRtablets.

Drug excipient compatibility studies:

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION:

Formulation	Gliclazide (mg)	Sodium alginate (mg)	Conc. Of Acetic acid (v/v)	Conc. Of NaHCO ₃ (mg)	Concentration of cross linking agent (g)	Volume of curing reagent	Curing time (hr)	Conc. Of Sodium alginate (g/ml)	Egg shell solution (ml)
F1	200	200	1.5	36	0.1	150	48	2	-
F2	200	200	1.5	55.55	0.1	150	48	2	-
F3	200	200	1.5	67	0.1	150	48	2	-
F4	200	150	1.5	55.55	0.1	150	48	2	-
F5	200	100	1.5	55.55	0.1	150	48	2	-
F6	200	200	1.5	55.55	-	150	48	2	0.1

Standard calibration curve data of gliclazide at 226.5 nm

S.No	Concentration (µg/ml)	Absorbance (X ± S.D)
1	0	0
2	2	0.09±0.004
3	4	0.175±0.006
4	6	0.249±0.003
5	8	0.336±0.028
6	10	0.415±0.034

The drug interactions studies between the drug and polymer were carried out by subjecting to IR studies. The IR spectra of gliclazide and its formulation with egg shell were showed bending (vibration) was observed in case of gliclazide and its microcapsules at 1593.37 cm⁻¹ and 1594.98 cm⁻¹, 1522.53 cm⁻¹, 1512.24 cm⁻¹ respectively.

The above peaks clearly indicated that there was no chemical incompatibility between drug and the polymers.

CALIBRATION CURVE OF GLICLAZIDE IN 0.1 N HCL AT 226.5NM

Recovery studies of Gliclazide

S.No	Excipient	Drug : Excipient ratio	Amount estimated (mg)	% Recovery
1	Sodium alginate	1:1	8.878	89.87
2	Sodium bicarbonate	1:2.5	8.783	88.91
3	Sodium alginate + Sodium bicarbonate	1:1:2.5	9.123	92.35

Comparative percentage drug release of gliclazide floating microcapsules formulated by employing different concentrations of sodium bicarbonate.

Time (hr)	Concentration of sodium bicarbonate (%w/w)		
	%Drug released ($\bar{X} \pm S.D$)		
	36 (F1)	55.55 (F2)	67 (F3)
1	2.073±0.8	26.861±0.7	25.625±0.3
2	6.155±0.7	34.280±0.6	44.087±0.2
3	8.079±0.5	42.902±0.8	54.654±0.7
4	14.085±0.6	50.844±0.3	65.060±0.5
5	20.123±0.4	54.976±0.4	92.284±0.7
6	26.195±0.9	59.711±0.5	-
7	32.3±0.5	62.872±0.8	-

8	38.438±0.7	67.647±0.6	-
9	44.827±0.6	73.029±0.5	-
10	51.033±0.4	86.550±0.7	-
11	-	95.740±0.4	-

Cumulative release profiles of gliclazide floating microcapsules formulated by employing different concentrations of sodium bicarbonate.

Zero order plots of gliclazide floating microcapsules formulated by employing different concentrations of sodium bicarbonate.

First order plots of gliclazide floating microcapsules formulated by employing different concentrations of sodium bicarbonate.

Peppas plots of gliclazide floating microcapsules formulated by employing different concentrations of sodium bicarbonate.

Release kinetics of gliclazide floating microcapsules formulated by employing different concentrations of sodium bicarbonate.

Concentration of sodium bicarbonate (%w/w)	Correlation coefficient				Release kinetics			Exponential coefficient (n)
	Zero order	First order	Higuchi	Peppas	K mg/hr	T50 (hr)	T90 (hr)	
36 (F3)	0.986	0.959	0.9709	0.9975	1.461±0.3	10.7	19.2	0.9963
55.55 (F4)	0.911	0.888	0.9853	0.9862	2.783±0.4	5.5	9.9	0.5061
67 (F5)	0.982	0.893	0.9683	0.9985	5.594±0.3	2.8	5.0	0.7418

Physical parameters of gliclazide floating microcapsules formulated by employing different concentrations of sodium bicarbonate

Concentration of sodium bicarbonate (%w/w)	Floating lag time (sec)	Floating time (hr)	Drug content (mg)		% Drug entrapment efficiency
			Theoretical	Practical	
			36 (F3)	35±0.3	
55.55 (F4)	25±0.3	>12	10	9.22	92.2
67 (F5)	15±0.3	>12	10	9.39	93.9

Flow properties of gliclazide floating microcapsules formulated by different concentrations of sodium bicarbonate

Concentration of sodium bicarbonate (%w/w)	Bulk density	Tapped density (mg/ml)	Carr's index (%)	Hausner's ratio	Angle of repose (°)
36 (F3)	0.286±.05	0.339±.03	15.6	1.185	25.64
55.55 (F4)	0.295±.045	0.353±.04	16.43	1.196	25.28
67 (F5)	0.268±.031	0.317±.02	15.45	1.182	23.22

Comparative percentage drug release profiles of gliclazide floating microcapsules formulated with various core: coat ratios

Time (hr)	Core : Coat ratio		
	%Drug released ($\bar{X} \pm \text{S.D}$)		
	1:1 (F2)	1:0.75 (F4)	1:0.5 (F6)
1	26.861±0.5	27.37±0.2	29.624±0.2
2	34.280±0.2	35.809±0.6	35.895±0.5
3	42.902±0.6	44.513±0.4	43.799±0.3
4	50.844±0.8	51.3±0.8	50.364±0.8
5	54.976±0.3	58.415±0.5	58.855±0.7
6	59.711±0.5	63.097±0.6	73.280±0.5
7	62.872±0.3	68.529±0.4	81.938±0.6
8	67.647±0.6	78.613±0.6	93.26±0.5
9	73.029±0.4	95.032±0.4	-
10	86.550±0.7	-	-
11	95.740±0.5	-	-

Cumulative release profiles of gliclazide floating microcapsules formulated with various core: coat ratios

Zero order plots of gliclazide floating microcapsules formulated with various core: coat ratios.

First order plots of gliclazide floating microcapsules formulated with various core: coat ratios

Peppas plots of gliclazide floating microcapsules formulated with various core: coat ratios

Core : Coat Ratio	Correlation coefficient				Release kinetics			Exponential coefficient (n)
	Zero order	First order	Higuchi	Peppas	K mg/hr	T50 (hr)	T90 (hr)	
1:1 (F2)	0.911	0.888	0.9853	0.9862	2.783±0.	5.5	9.9	0.5061
1:0.75 (F4)	0.935	0.880	0.9855	0.9625	3.233±0.3	4.6	8.3	0.5345
1:0.5 (F5)	0.9596	0.9257	0.9562	0.9701	3.658±0.3	4.1	7.4	0.5587

Physical parameters of gliclazide floating microcapsules formulated with various core: coat ratios.

Core : Coat ratio	Floating lag time (sec)	Floating time (hr)	Drug content (mg)		% Drug entrapment efficiency
			Theoretical	Practical	
1:1 (F2)	25±0.2	>12	10	9.22	92.2
1:0.75 (F4)	25±0.3	>12	10	9.46	94.6
1:0.5 (F5)	20±0.2	>12	10	9.58	95.8

Flow properties of gliclazide floating microcapsules formulated with various core: coat ratios

Core : Coat ratio	Bulk density	Tapped density (mg/ml)	Carr's index (%)	Hausner's ratio	Angle of repose(°)
1:1 (F2)	0.253±.03	0.286±.03	11.5	1.130	21.52
1:0.75 (F4)	0.269±.04	0.312±.02	13.7	1.159	23.22
1:0.5 (F5)	0.286±.02	0.339±.05	15.6	1.185	25.64

Percentage drug release profile of gliclazide floating microcapsules formulated by employing Egg shell solution as curing agent.

Time (hr)	Egg shell solution as curing agent
	%Drug released ($\bar{X} \pm S.D$) (F6)
1	7.428±0.4
2	15.254±0.8
3	24.609±0.6
4	32.247±0.3
5	40.917±0.5
6	50.059±0.7
7	58.401±0.2
8	64.806±0.8
9	67.070±0.5
10	70.619±0.6
11	78.755±0.4
12	95.580±0.5

Cumulative release profiles of gliclazide floating microcapsules by employing Egg shell solution as curing agent.

First order plots of gliclazide floating microcapsules formulated by employing Egg shell solution as curingagent.

Peppas plots of gliclazide floating microcapsules formulated by employing Egg shell solution as curingagent.

Release kinetics of gliclazide floating microcapsules formulated by employing egg shell solution as curing reagent . Physical parameters of gliclazide floating microcapsules formulated by

curing reagent solution	Correlation coefficient				Release kinetics			Exponential coefficient (n)
	Zero order	First order	Higuchi	Peppas	K mg/hr	T50 (hr)	T90 (hr)	
Egg shell solution	0.9922	0.8108	0.9878	0.9968	2.363±0.3	6.5	11.7	0.9984

Comparative percentage drug release profiles of optimized gliclazide microcapsules with different curing reagents and gliclazide marketed MR tablet (Diamicron) in 0.1N HCl (pH-1.2)

Time in hrs	%Drug released ($\bar{X} \pm \bar{S.D}$)	
	Egg shell solution	Diamicron
1	7.428±0.4	14.974±0.4
2	15.254±0.8	31.16±0.4
3	24.609±0.6	54.013±0.2
4	32.247±0.3	71.904±0.6
5	40.917±0.5	89.281±0.5
6	50.059±0.7	95.587±0.3
7	58.401±0.2	-
8	64.806±0.8	-
9	67.070±0.5	-
10	70.619±0.6	-
11	78.755±0.4	-
12	95.580±0.5	-

Comparative drug release profiles of optimized gliclazide microcapsules with egg shell solution and gliclazide marketed MR tablet (Diamicon) in 0.1N HCl (pH-1.2)

Zero order plots for optimized gliclazide microcapsules with egg shell solution and gliclazide marketed MR tablet (Diamicon) in 0.1N HCl (pH-1.2)

First order plots for optimized gliclazide microcapsules with egg shell solution and gliclazide marketed MR tablet (Diamicon) in 0.1N HCl (pH-1.2)

Release kinetics of optimized gliclazide floating microcapsules with egg shell solutions and gliclazide marketed MR tablet (Diamicon) in 0.1N HCl (pH-1.2)

Different curing reagent solutions	Correlation coefficient				Release kinetics			Exponential coefficient (n)	Similarity factor (f2)
	Zero order	First order	Higuchi	Peppas	K mg/hr	T5 (h)	T90 (hr)		
Egg shell solution (A)	0.9922	0.8108	0.9878	0.9968	2.363	6.5	11.7	0.9984	24.26
Diamicon (B)	0.9941	0.9320	0.9543	0.9958	5.263	2.9	5.3	0.9963	(A&B)

Statistical treatment for floating lag time of Gliclazide floating microcapsules formulated by employing different concentrations of Sodium bicarbonate. Each point refers to mean ($\bar{X} \pm S.D$) i.e n=3

Parameter	Sodium bicarbonate (36%)	Sodium bicarbonate (55.55%)	Sodium bicarbonate (67%)	ANNOVA (One-way)		
				Calculated F value	Degree of freedom	Significance
Floating lagtime	35±0.3	25±0.3	15±0.3	3600	2,6	P<0.01

Statistical treatment for release rate constant of Gliclazide floating microcapsules formulated by employing different core: coat ratios. Each point refers to mean ($\bar{X} \pm S.D$) i.e n=3

Parameter	core: coat (1:1)	Core:coat (1:0.75)	core: coat (1:0.5)	ANNOVA (One-way)		
				Calculated F value	Degree of freedom	Significance
K	2.783±0.4	3.233±0.3	3.658±0.3	42030	2,6	P<0.0001

Statistical treatment for release rate constant of Gliclazide floating microcapsules formulated by employing different curing reagent solutions. Each point refers to mean ($\bar{X} \pm S.D$) i.e n=3

Parameter	Synthetic CaCO ₃	Egg shell	ANNOVA (One-way)		
			Calculated F value	Degree of freedom	Significance
K	2.783±0.4	2.363±0.3	7676	1,4	P<0.0001

Statistical treatment for release rate constant of optimized gliclazide floating microcapsules formulated by employing Synthetic CaCO₃ as curing reagent solution and marketed formulation (Diamicron). Each point refers to mean ($\bar{X} \pm S.D$) i.e n=3

Parameter	Marketed tablet (Diamicron)	Synthetic CaCO ₃	t-test (non-parametric)	
			Degree of freedom	Significance
K	5.263±0.4	2.783±0.4	4	P=0.0011

Statistical treatment for release rate constant of optimized gliclazide floating microcapsules formulated by employing egg shell solution and as curing reagent solution and marketed formulation (Diamicron). Each point refers to mean ($\bar{X} \pm S.D$) i.e n=3

Parameter	Marketed tablet (Diamicron)	Egg shell	t-test (non-parametric)	
			Degree of freedom	Significance
K	5.263±0.4	2.363±0.4	4	P<0.0001

IR spectra of gliclazide

Photomicrographs of gliclazide floating microspheres prepared by employing egg shell solution as curing agent.

In the present investigation an attempt was made to develop gliclazide floating microcapsules by employing natural cross linking agents i.e egg shell solution, with a view to prolong the gastric residence time. Orifice ionic gelation technique was used to prepare microcapsules by employing sodium alginate as polymer. Studies were carried out on influence of formulation variables on drug release rate, entrapment efficiencies and floating behavior. The formulated microcapsules were characterized for their micrometric properties, floating properties, drug loading and entrapment efficiency and invitro drug release studies. The gliclazide microcapsules

formulated by employing the core: coat (1:1) and having the composition 1.5%v/v acetic acid, 55.55%w/w sodium bicarbonate, 2% w/v sodium alginate, 150ml of 0.1M egg shell solution as curing agent, and by maintaining 48hrs curing time showed required drug release upto 12hrs.

The following conclusions were made from these experimental results:

Floating microcapsules of gliclazide were prepared by employing orifice ionic gelation method.

IR spectral studies revealed that there was no incompatibility between the polymers employed and

the druggliclazide. The formulated microcapsules showed good Micromeritic properties.

The floating lag time was dependent on concentration of gas forming agent and 55.55% sodium bicarbonate was found to be optimum concentration.

The rate of drug release was dependent on polymer concentration and core: coat (1:1) was found to be optimum for slow and complete drug release.

The drug release rate followed zero order kinetics and controlled by non-fickian diffusion.

The optimized formulation is compared with a natural cross-linking agent and such microcapsules exhibited similar dissolution profiles with that of synthetic cross-linking agent calcium carbonate.

The optimized formulations with natural cross-linking agent compared with marketed formulations shows high sustainability in drug release.

Gliclazide microcapsules formulated by employing synthetic and natural cross-linking agents were found to be effective in reducing blood glucose levels compared to pure drug and all the formulations are pharmacodynamically equal.

Recommendations:

Stability studies:

The stability studies can be conducted on the selected microcapsules as per ICH guidelines.

Other natural calcium sources:

Other natural calcium sources can be identified which are bio-degradable and acceptable.

Microencapsulation with other drugs:

This technique can be used in the formulation of other drugs.

REFERENCES:

1. Fu Y et al. Orally fast disintegrating tablets: developments, technologies, taste masking and clinical studies. *Crit Rev Ther Drug Carrier Syst.* 2004; 21: 433-476.
2. Lindgren S et al. Prevalence of swallowing complaints and clinical findings among 50-79-year-old men and women in an urban population. *Dysphagia.* 1991; 6: 187-192.
3. Kahrilas PJ. Anatomy, physiology and pathophysiology of dysphagia. *Acta Otorhinolaryngol Belg.* 1994; 48: 97-117. PMID:8209687
4. Mehta K et al. An emerging trend in oral drug delivery technology: rapid disintegrating tablets. *J Pharm Sci Technol.* 2010; 2: 318-329.
5. Sreenivas SA et al. Orodispersible tablets: New-drug delivery system – A review. *Indian J Pharm Educ Res.* 2005; 39(4): 177-181
6. US Food and Drug Administration, CDER Data Standards Manual. 2003.
7. European Pharmacopoeia. 5th ed. Strasbourg, France: 2006. pg. 628.
8. Chang RK et al. Fast-dissolving tablets. *Pharm Technol.* 2000; 24: 52-58.
9. Parakh SR et al. A review of mouth dissolving tablet technologies. *Pharm Technol.* 2003; 27: 92-100.
10. Kuchekar B S et al. Mouth dissolving tablets: a novel drug delivery system. *Pharma Times.* 2003; 35: 7-9